

Original Paper

The Distributed Electron

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Abstract: A 'Hidden Variables' model of the electron is developed based on distributed interacting acoustic spin structures in a massive ether. Standard quantum mechanical results can be replicated but have a very different interpretation. The wave function of normal QM becomes an indicator of the amplitude and phase of discrete vortices (here called Field Rotators or FRs) distributed on a cubic spatial grid. The 'mass' of each FR is a measure of its energy content and is given by $\psi_i^* \psi_i$; the total mass of the structure (particle) is the summation over all FRs. Discrete spin angular momenta can likewise be summed to give $\hbar/2$. Eigen-energies reflect slowing of the FR rotation rate. FRs are found to have phases alternating by π radians; a feature which explains the second spatial derivative in Schrödinger's equation and leads to the Pauli exclusion principle. Interpreting underlying phase variation across structures as energy flows leads to the correct values for orbital angular momentum. Phase harmony for moving structures requires Lorentz length contraction and time dilation. Free particle energies agree with the Dirac equation. It is submitted that the model provides a credible and insightful ontology for Quantum Mechanics.

Keywords: Hidden Variables, Real Wave Quantum Mechanics, Quantum ontology, Spin Angular Momentum, Orbital Angular Momentum, Special Relativity, Exclusion Principle

1. Introduction, Motivation and Postulates

1.1. Motivation In 1965, in his book on Special Relativity, David Bohm wrote [1]: "...the transformation between 'rest energy' and other forms of energy, implies that we shall eventually have to understand the so-called 'elementary' particles as structures arising in relatively invariant patterns of movement occurring at a still lower level than that of these particles." Developments in Quantum Field Theory (QFT) and the Standard Model since that time have been dramatic. Particles are now viewed as quantized excitations of fields, but 'excitations' fall short of the definitive structures envisaged by Bohm. We deal with their properties but have no clear picture of what they 'are'¹. In this paper we seek to realise Bohm's prediction.

The direction of travel in the present study is not typical. Rather than starting with QM/QFT and trying to interpret it, we develop a candidate theory from some basic postulates and try to establish the extent to which it leads to quantum mechanical behaviour. This approach has proved very successful, as the developed theory is isomorphic with the Schrödinger/Dirac equations. Full quantitative comparison is hindered because the numerical calculations required are too large for a realistic system such as the hydrogen atom. The work has mainly been restricted to highly constrained Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potentials.

1.2. 'Real' Waves The theory has been called Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM).

The term 'Real' is used simply because the building blocks of the theory are longitudinal compression waves (i.e. acoustic waves) whose reality it is difficult to argue against, in contrast with the superluminal de Broglie phase waves or the probabilistically interpreted Schrödinger waves. To support these waves we posit a massive all-pervasive medium (an ether²) - massive in the sense that waves within the medium can be associated with energy and momentum. We anticipate that the mass of a 'particle' (for us to be an extended structure) will only arise to the extent that energy-momentum within the wave structure remains localized.

¹ For a full discussion of the ontic interpretation of QFT the reader is referred to the article in the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy on Quantum Field Theory [2].

² We are bolstered by Einstein's comments in 1920 [3] "...the special theory of relativity does not compel us to deny ether. We may assume the existence of an ether; only we must give up ascribing a definite state of motion to it..." We are, of course, beholden to show how the model is compatible with the measurable consequences of Special Relativity (SR).

1.3. The Interaction of Real Waves

It is well established [4],[5], [6], [7] that plane acoustic waves intercepting with specific correlation between direction and phase (Phase Direction Correlation, or PDC) can give rise to vortices having angular momentum. We will call these vortices 'Field Rotators' or just FRs.

The animation [OLR1](#) shows the summed amplitudes of 4 plane waves having directions $\pm x$ and $\pm y$, and having phases correlated to these directions. The integer x,y intercepts are nodes around which zones of high density rotate clockwise or anti-clockwise depending on the correlation. They have angular momentum. Over the whole field the directions of rotation alternate so the net AM is zero.

A more rigorous analysis of acoustic spin has been made by Burns et al [4], using Lagrangian analysis. This is applied to the 4-wave prototype in [A](#). The key findings are that:

- the spin density does not depend on the density of the medium
- the spin density varies as the square of the amplitude
- the spin density is proportional to the frequency.

These are all features we would hope to find in an extended electron structure.

1.4. Further Postulates To progress the model we must make some postulates:

- Sources - without sources FRs will be transient because waves will eventually leave any 'structure', carrying energy with them. We could classify such waves as 'empty' because they are no longer in PDC with other waves and are no longer contributing to the mass and angular momentum. In a somewhat chicken and egg argument, we can surmise that if stable particles exist there will be a stochastic vacuum wave field full of these empty waves. But if this is the case then we can equally surmise that FRs can gain in amplitude by interacting with this field, perhaps through a resonant process. We simply postulate such a gain without further justification. Specifically, we postulate a gain which is proportional to the current amplitude and to the local strength of the vacuum gain field.
- FR Interaction - If FRs are to form a stable structure, there must be some form of interaction between them. The waves from which they are formed cannot simply pass through unchanged. Therefore, we postulate some non-linear behaviour, with a fixed fraction of the wave energy passing through them being absorbed and re-radiated as a spiral wave having the same sense and phase as the spin. We can quantify this using

a dimensionless interaction coefficient, say α , which is the ratio of the amplitude of the re-emitted spiral wave to the received PDC amplitude. We do not seek to justify the postulate at this stage, although, if true, it should eventually be possible to do so. We note that it has some similarities with Huygens principle, but here applied to discrete locations and with spiral rather than spherical re-emitted wavelets.

- Interpretation of Potential - The stochastic gain from the vacuum gives us a means of interpreting the 'potential', and the role it plays in shaping the eigenfunctions. Because our structures are extended we must abandon the concept of a Coulomb force between charged point particles while retaining some element of its mathematical content³. Instead, we postulate that a static potential describes a local modification of the vacuum gain field.
- Geometry of structures - if we seek a structure for an extended electron consisting of interacting FRs we must make some assumption about its spatial arrangement. In this paper we restrict ourselves to square grids in 2D or cubic structures in 3D, a decision forced upon us initially to make the calculations tractable⁴. Other geometrical structures are possible - indeed, we would require their existence to explain other 'particles'; but we have to start somewhere.

2. Stationary Structures - Calculation Method and Results

2.1. Method

2.1.1. Calculating Phase-Direction Correlated Contributions

Given a field of FRs, we must devise a method to calculate the combined PDC contribution of waves arriving at each FR from all the other FR locations. Although the waves are spiral we will approximate them as plane waves, since most FRs will be separated by a significant number of grid steps. We will only consider monochromatic waves.

Despite the need to take direction, phase and spin sense into account in calculating contributions from each source to the target, it turns out that these factors cancel out to a degree and we end up with two simple rules. For positive spin (anticlockwise) and wavelength λ the phase ϕ and amplitude A of the contribution from source S to target

³ A major advantage of this approach is that we can stop worrying about the 'self-energy' of the electron - the 'problem' is meaningless

⁴ Calculating the location of FRs over all space would be extremely expensive. Instead, we are going to insist that the centres fall on the grid.

T at a distance of d is given by:

$$\phi_T = -\phi_S - d/\lambda; \quad A_T = A_S/d \tag{1}$$

For negative spin i.e.clockwise, the rule is

$$\phi_T = \phi_S + d/\lambda; \quad A_T = A_S/d \tag{2}$$

These results are derived in B . It is a remarkable fact that, despite our concern about both the arriving direction and phase of waves passing through a target FR, in calculating PDC contributions these factors cancel out. We are left with simple phasor addition in the manner of Feynman, except here the sources and targets are at discrete locations rather than at all points in space-time⁵.

We have adopted the term 'Discrimination' to describe the process of summing all the source contributions at a target FR - we have 'spin-up discrimination' defined by Equation 1 and 'spin-down discrimination' for Equation 2⁶.

2.1.2. Eigenstructure Calculation

We consider only stationary states. We set up a grid of FR points separated by one wavelength. To illustrate the method we start by considering a one dimensional row of FRs, We can write a set of simultaneous equations for the contributions and gain at each grid point in the form of a matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_1 & \alpha & \alpha/2 & \alpha/3 & \dots \\ \alpha & V_2 & \alpha & \alpha/2 & \alpha/3 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \alpha/3 & \alpha/2 & \alpha & V_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \\ \dots \\ \psi_N \end{bmatrix} = \Lambda_E \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \\ \dots \\ \psi_N \end{bmatrix}$$

A background vacuum gain potential V_v is added to the potential i.e. $V_n = V_v + V(x)$ and this is written on the diagonals of the matrix. For example, the first equation reads:

$$V_1\psi_1 + \alpha\psi_2 + \alpha\psi_3/2 + \alpha\psi_4/3\dots = \Lambda_E\psi_1 \tag{3}$$

where α is the re-radiation coefficient. In this one dimensional case the geometric effect of the FR locations (the amplitude reduction following from the distance of separation)

⁵ If our approach leads to QM (it does!) could it provide some justification for the otherwise inexplicable success of the Feynman sum over paths procedure?

⁶ A potential issue with the discriminator approach is that to associate it with the AM of the FR, we must assume a balanced distribution of wave directions. For example, it would give a false high result for a standing wave along a single axis, even though no angular momentum is involved. The extent to which this might be a problem can only be assessed once we have a clearer idea about the form any stable structures might take.

Figure 1. Comparison of 1D results for SHO potential using RWQM and Schrödinger equation. Parameters chosen to show form similarity.

is completely specified by the harmonic series in α . This will not be true for higher dimensionalities, where much larger matrices are needed to encode the relationships. This is an eigenvalue problem, and its solutions should be structures (i.e. eigenvectors) which are consistent up to multiplication by a single (perhaps complex) eigenvalue, Λ_E . This only partially meets the required stability condition because we seek real eigenvalues of unit magnitude. However, it moves us forward. All the work described below is based on the Simple Harmonic Oscillator potential (SHO).

2.2. One Dimensional Systems We apply the method to 1D structures first, despite the fact that orthogonal contributions will be absent, meaning there is no AM. We do this because the results are particularly revealing of a feature which carries forward to higher dimensions. Solutions have been calculated using Python, Numpy and the Scipy eigs module. Although only results for SHO potentials are reported on in this paper the method has been applied with equal success to the 1D Infinite Square Well and Finite Square Well potentials. A selection of solutions for SHO are shown in Figure 1a. For comparison, results obtained using a standard Finite Difference solution of the Schrödinger equation¹ are shown in Figure 1b. The parameters used were selected to facilitate the comparison: the results are essentially identical.

As shown in Figure 2, eigenvalues found by RWQM can be made to exactly replicate

¹ The published program [8] uses a non-dimensional form of Schrödinger's equation based on a distance L which is the characteristic size of the well potentials it treats. This distance is discretized into the required number of steps. To render it comparable with the RWQM calculation the discretization step must be set to the RWQM wavelength.

Figure 2. Eigenvalues

Figure 3. Close up of phase for first eigenfunction

those of the Schrödinger equation by adopting an unphysical value for α i.e. > 1 . These results are included to illustrate the mathematical isomorphism between the RWQM process and the Schrödinger equation. The unphysical value for α arises from the unphysical nature of the 1D calculation. Contributions from most FRs are missing and this is compensated for by increasing the value of α .

Given the very different conceptual basis for RWQM and Schrödinger's equation, the agreement between results is startling and requires explanation. Some light on the isomorphism is cast by Figure 3 which shows that for RWQM the phase of consecutive FRs alternates i.e. they differ by $\approx \pi$. This 'Phase Alternation' (PA) was masked in Figure 1a by plotting $\psi^*\psi$, and proves to be a key feature of RWQM. From Equation 3 we can see that in 1D, part of the RWQM procedure amounts to the summation of two suitably scaled

Figure 4. Effect of Potential on Curvature

harmonic series (one from either direction). Such series do not converge, but the phase alternation in the results has given rise instead to two alternating harmonic series and these *do* converge. In particular, contributions from adjacent FRs, are out of phase, or negative, with respect to the FR in question. Since these are the leading terms in the series, they dominate its sign, leading us to conclude that the amplitude of an FR is always reduced by contributions from other FRs.

The manner in which Phase Alternation leads to the spatial isomorphism with Schrödinger's equation is illustrated in Figure 4. In the central portion we consider a hypothetical situation where gains are exactly balanced by negative summed contribution along a row of FRs subjected to some uniform and critical potential gain field. In the left hand part we reduce the potential below this critical value and consider the FR at point A (the arguments will apply equally to all FRs of course). The FR is no longer receiving enough gain to remain in a flat row of FRs. To balance gains and losses requires that the negative contributions from other FRs must be reduced *pro rata* and this can only be achieved if the amplitude of the adjacent FRs are on average lower. Viewed over the whole line we see that this requires negative curvature of the amplitude envelope. This explains the sinusoidal behaviour in the central region of low potential in an SHO potential. The right hand portion shows the reversed situation, when the gain field is too high. In this case an FR at C can only be in balance if the adjacent FRs are on average higher, which leads to positive curvature and accounts for the zones of decaying exponential envelope in the outer

regions of the SHO potential.²

Thus, the RWQM model can achieve the same results as normal quantum mechanics with regard to the shape of eigenvectors (structures) and their eigenvalues, but without recourse to an explanation which implies that even in a stationary state with no angular momentum, the shape of the wave function is somehow controlled by a second derivative derived from a momentum i.e. $p^2/2m$.

Figure 5. Close up of central region for 2nd SHO Energy Level. Phase Alternation 'flips' at the centre point

Stationary state solutions of Schrödinger’s equation involve continuous rotation in the complex plane. Sometimes the real part is positive and sometimes negative. The important feature for RWQM is not the actual sign, but the locations of the nodes. At a node we find that the alternation 'flips' as shown in Figure 5.

We will return to the relationships with the equations of QM later in Section 4.2, but meanwhile we can draw the following conclusions:

- In 1 dimension RWQM and the Time Independent Schrödinger equation are isomorphic.
- The wave function of RWQM is a Discrete Alternating Function with $\psi^*\psi$ at the FRs

² As an interesting aside, we note that the second differential of any well behaved function can be estimated by first discretizing it, then alternating signs and calculating the summed contributions as we have done. The empirical expression is

$$\frac{d^2\psi_i}{dx^2} = 8 \ln 2 \left(\frac{\hat{F}_A * \psi}{2 \ln 2} - f(x_i) \right) \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \tag{4}$$

where \hat{F}_A represents an harmonic series kernel, the asterisk indicates convolution and Δx is the discretization interval. The reason for this is not known to us.

'enveloped' by the continuous Schrödinger values.

We are now in a position to move on to 2D application of RWQM.

2.3. 2-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator

Moving to 2 dimensions expands contributions to include those from diagonally separated FRs on the grid which may not be in PDC. It also places large demands on the computations because the matrix must represent the relationship of each FR to all of the others³. Any structures found must be confined to the central zone of the grid of FRs so that the amplitudes around the boundaries are essentially zero, otherwise there would be significant edge effects. In practice, this means slowly changing potentials such as the Coulomb potential in a hydrogen atom⁴ are beyond the current scope, and attention remains focussed on the SHO potential. Sufficient containment only arises for very high SHO potentials.

Resulting eigenvector structures for an 80×80 grid are given in Figure 6. (The use of $\alpha = 1/137$ is reasonable but entirely whimsical at this stage.) The echelon form reflects the degeneracy of the eigenvalues corresponding to these structures¹. Typically quoted eigenfunctions (e.g. on the St Andrews website [here](#)) are only partially comparable. Some forms are exactly replicated, but as will be shown below, others arise from the superposition of structures with orbital angular momentum to give non-rotational states. A similar finding has been noted when the eigs method is applied using standard Finite Difference methods [9].

An immediate conclusion is that the isomorphism between RWQM solutions and those of the Schrödinger equation carries forward into 2 dimensions. The new feature which is introduced is the phase variation across the FRs. This has two components:

- Figure 7 is a close up showing the amplitude in colour contours and the phase of FRs as the small arrows. It is clear that phase alternation (in both grid directions) is also a feature in 2-D.

³ For example, if the physical size of the grid is 80×80 (as it is for the results quoted herein) the matrix must have dimensions of 6400×6400 , which is 40,960,000 entries. Each entry must incorporate the distance and angle between itself and the target FR. Unlike the linear case, contributions will typically be complex.

⁴ As will be shown in Section 4.4 the grid size required to match RWQM with reality is the Compton wavelength for the electron. For a spherical structure such as the $n = 3$ orbital of a hydrogen atom, we would have to calculate out to approximately 200 Compton wavelengths, involving 64 million FRs and we have to calculate the interaction of each of them with all the others.

¹ An unfortunate feature of the eigenvalue software is that results can be superpositions of degenerate states, and members of degenerate groups can be produced in different orders from run to run. The order of the structures given in Figure 6 has been adopted as standard and they have been numbered from 1 to 15

Figure 6. 80x80 grid, $\alpha = 1/137$, SHO constant $C = 4e-6$

Figure 7. Close up of phase arrows showing alternating phases. FRs are located at grid intersections

Figure 8. Full scale showing variation of phase direction across the structure

- Figure 8 shows a similar full scale plot for one of the structures. An underlying phase variation is clearly visible. This is studied in Section 3.1 below.

It is instructive to compare the density field of a structure with the simplistic plane wave model shown in OLR1. This is done for the central region of Structure 1 and is shown in OLR2. The key feature is that there are no longer cells of opposite spin. Instead there is a checkerboard pattern of alternating phases with the same spin direction.

2.3.1. 2-D Eigenvalues

Eigenvalue data for the structures shown in Figure 6 are plotted in Figure 9. They were initially calculated with $\lambda = 1$ and V_v adjusted to ensure that they were of unit magnitude. The following observations are made:

- eigenvalues are complex, with 9a showing their phase angles.
- eigenvalues show the same degeneracy grouping for 2D SHO as predicted by the solution of Schrödinger's equation
- plotting the average energies for each degeneracy group (the blue dots) shows that the spacing of the phases is effectively linear².

The Schrödinger picture views the eigenvalue phase angle as an indicator of the particle energy. It accepts that the wave function rotates in the complex plane and extracts the energy using the operator $E \leftrightarrow i\hbar\partial/\partial t$. Our complex eigenvalues imply that the

² There is a small second order variation which could easily be due to edge effects as the sizes of the structures increase.

Figure 9. The blue points are the averages of the degeneracy groups to illustrate linearity of eigen-energies

(a) Phase angle ϕ with $\lambda = 1$

(b) λ to make $\phi = 0$

(c) V_v for unit Eigenvalue

(d) Energy ratio for unit Eigenvalue

contributions received from other FRs do not match the current phase of an FR. We cannot allow this interpretation because:

- our FRs are nothing more than a sum of the waves they receive. They 'are what they eat'! If we want to describe a physical stationary state, then we must have an eigenvalue of 1
- RWQM is already based on structures rotating at a particular frequency. If some additional energy (i.e. frequency) is to be associated with them, then it must be represented as a modification of that existing frequency.

Together, these arguments suggest that we should seek real eigenvalues by modifying the rotation frequency. To be clear, this is not just a matter of changing the frequency and adjusting the grid spacing accordingly. What is required is to adjust the frequency and hence the wavelength λ for the existing grid until we find a real eigenvalue. Perhaps surprisingly, this proves to be possible and has been done using an optimization program. Numeric results for the required wavelength are plotted in Figure 9b. The eigenvalues have been made to have unit magnitude by adjusting V_v to the values plotted in Figure 9c. Finally, the implied energy ratios ω/ω_0 (the reciprocal of the wavelengths) are plotted in Figure 9d.

Using the optimized λ it is possible to build a kernel which can be convolved with the structure many times without perceptible change - the structures are stable in both space and time up to the underlying rotation frequency. Our interpretation is clear: a structure has a lower energy because its frequency of rotation has been reduced from the 'free particle' value. In this respect RWQM results (albeit qualitative) are similar to results from the Dirac equation, since this also gives energies as some fraction of the rest mass energy³ $mc^2 = \hbar\omega$.

2.3.2. Antimatter

If the structures in Figure 6 describe matter solutions, what is antimatter? The method described in Section 2.1.2 does not find eigensolutions which are stable under inverted potential curves. However, the following symmetry translations reveal the possible existence of such alternatives. If we

³ For example, the Dirac solution for the energy of the hydrogen atom with $Z = 1$, $n_r = 0$, $j = 1/2$ is given by

$$E(=\hbar\omega) = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}}}}$$

The fraction is 0.9999733746 of the rest mass. The equivalent Schrödinger energy is $\approx 2.6625398 \times 10^{-5}$ times the rest mass which is $\approx 13.605eV$.

- take the complex conjugate of a structure
- reverse the spin being used in the discrimination process, and
- invert the potential curve so the highest gain is at the central point

we find structures which, upon convolution with the appropriately modified kernel, leave the phase of each FR unchanged (i.e. the eigenvalues are real). However, they are not stable under repeated convolution. This behaviour requires further investigation.

2.3.3. 3D Structures

The calculation method can be extended to three dimensions with a cubic grid of FRs. For the SHO potential the spring constant must be very high to confine structures in a small enough space to be calculable. Sample 3D visualisations OLR3 and OLR4 can be downloaded from [here](#) and [here](#) and will run in a browser. The size of the dots are scaled to the magnitude squared while the colouring is indicative of underlying phase, phase alternation having been removed. Within the spatial constraints they match Schrödinger solution forms well.

3. Angular Momentum There are two quite different aspects to motion in RWQM:

- motion of entire structures through the underlying medium. This is examined in Section 4.
- 'motion' within the structure itself.

Historically (but see [10],[11]), physics has not distinguished between these forms, starting with the Bohr model based on massive particles in fixed orbits, through the vague concept of probability flow, and on to the deBroglie-Bohm pilot wave theory, again of a massive particle being 'guided' by a Schrödinger wave function. The common factor is a point mass for which we can determine some tangential motion giving rise to orbital angular momentum. RWQM requires that we abandon this picture.

3.1. Orbital Angular Momenta In RWQM, we attribute the concept of mass to the squared amplitude of the FRs, which are distributed in a stable extended structure. Can we envisage the whole structure and its constituent FRs rotating bodily around the proton within a fixed 'ether' frame? No, because it would destroy the balanced phase interactions between the FRs. We must look elsewhere for an understanding of orbital angular momentum and our starting point is the usual guidance equation of quantum mechanics[12][13] associating

Figure 10. Structure 1. Small arrows in (a) indicate the phase of the FRs. The momentum vectors in (b) are the product of the phase gradient and the magnitude of the FRs. ($C= 9e-6, \alpha = 1/137$)

momentum with a phase gradient, namely

$$\dot{x} = \left(\frac{1}{m} \right) \nabla S$$

where S is the phase in the polar form of the wave function:

$$\psi = R \exp \frac{iS}{\hbar}, \quad R, S \in R$$

We have previously noted that our structures exhibit spatial phase variation (see for example Figure 8). We can calculate the phase gradient at each FR, multiply it by $\psi^*\psi$ for that FR, resolve the resulting 'momentum' into radial and tangential components and sum over all FRs.

This is done for Structure 1 in Figure 10a and the results are presented in Figure 10b. As expected, the orbital angular momentum is zero, but there is an additional momentum pointing to the centre which is discussed below.

The same process applied to structures 2 and 3 is complicated because the eigenvalue software has found superpositions of states with and without AM. By taking suitable combinations of these solutions it is possible to construct a pure AM state. This is illustrated in Figure 11. The angular momenta calculated from the phase gradients are ± 1 to a high degree of accuracy.

The 5th state is pure and gives an angular momentum of zero as shown in Figure 12. Finally, structures 4 and 6 are pure non-rotational states. Their superposition is illustrated

Figure 11. Results from eigenvalue calculations give mixtures of AM base states (left). These are optimally superposed to give maximum AM (centre). Momenta calculated from the phase gradient (right). The contour in the momentum diagram is $\psi^*\psi$. Top row Structure 2, bottom row structure 3. The calculated Angular Momentum components are ± 0.9999 . ($C= 9e-6$, $\alpha = 1/137$)

(a) Original Phase/amp

(b) AM superposition

(c) Momentum

Figure 12. Structure 5 $C=9e-6$, $\alpha = 1/137$ **(a)** Magnitude and Phase**(b)** Momenta

in Figure 13 and the AM is ± 2 . These are the correct AMs for 2D SHO states. (See for example [14]) We can conclude that the guidance equation can be applied to RWQM structures and gives the correct result for orbital AM.

But it is reasonable to ask 'What is moving?' The FRs are stationary, and their mass is unchanging with time. The momentum must be attributable to the tangential component of the energy flux in the circulating patterns, clearly visible in the Figures. This explanation has previously been provided by Ohanion [10] who showed that the momentum density in a Dirac field contains two terms, one associated with the translational motion of the electron (for us a structure) and the second associated with a circulating flow of energy in the wave field in the rest frame. RWQM attaches a real interpretation to this circulation; it is the flux of wave energy from FR to FR, and an energy flux is the same thing as a momentum.

But we have more: if the tangential component represents an energy flow, then so must the radial component. Such a flow is to be anticipated because the basic RWQM model is of energy transfer from outer zones where the potential gains are greater than some critical value, i.e. sources, towards inner zones where the potential gains are lower, i.e. sinks. It should be possible to treat this situation in terms of energy and momentum conservation.

In summary, RWQM coupled with the guidance equation gives the correct values for orbital AM, but the ontology is completely different from the old QM interpretations. The internal motion of the electron does not relate to a massive point particle in normal motion. Instead, the phase gradient across FRs is indicative of the flow of energy taking place within the structure.

Figure 13. Results for structures 4 and 6. The calculated Angular Momentum components are ± 1.99998 . ($C= 9e-6$, $\alpha = 1/137$)

(a) Original Phase/amplitude

(b) AM superposition

(c) Momentum/amplitude

3.2. *Spin Angular Momentum* In Section 1.3 the possibility of understanding spin angular momentum as something other than 'intrinsic' was introduced as a motivation for pursuing the RQWM model. OLR1 showed the 'spin' resulting from four orthogonal waves in PDC. The red dots in OLR1 indicate the motion of the centres of mass (COM) of the cell. We now look at how these were found and their relevance to spin AM. The method used was to find the lowest value of the summed amplitudes over a single cycle, and subtract this value ($-2\sqrt{2}$ for four orthogonal waves) to give a distribution of positive densities. A standard COM calculation applied to this distribution shows that it moves in circular motion with radius $r_{COM} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.112539$ based on a unit cell ($\lambda = 1$). For a different wavelength we have $r_{COM} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$. Adding more sets of four orthogonal PDC waves rotated by various angles increases the amplitude but gives the same radius for the COM.

When considering the wave field within a cell of one of the structures of Section 2.3, the above method fails, because many of the waves are not in PDC. To see this, consider a cell of perfect PDC waves and then add a single high amplitude wave out of PDC. The low point of the cycle is reduced considerably so the radius of the centre of mass is reduced, despite the fact that the angular momentum should be unchanged by an extra wave in a single direction. To progress, we make the following postulate:

- the radius of the centre of mass for discriminated structures is the same as for pure PDC (i.e. $\frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$).

Having this as a postulate is rather unsatisfactory as we would prefer to demonstrate its validity. However, accepting the postulate can lead to the correct spin AM. Setting $c = 1$

$$r_{COM} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}}$$

Distance travelled in one circulation:

$$d = 2\pi r_{COM} = 2\pi \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Time for one revolution:

$$t = \frac{2\pi}{\omega}$$

Velocity:

$$v = \frac{d}{t} = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\omega}{2\pi}$$

To get the correct total spin AM requires that the mass used in the further calculation be $m_{FR} = \psi^*\psi$, i.e. the mass of the FR, despite the fact that we used the radius calculated from the COM for the underlying wave mass which is based on ψ rather than $\psi * \psi$. This seems curious, but is in line with the findings of Burns et al [4] as applied in A which

indicated that spin density is dependent on the square of the amplitude, rather than just the amplitude. Conditionally accepting this, the angular momentum is:

$$AM = m_{FR} v_{rCOM} = m_{FR} \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} = \frac{m_{FR}\lambda^2\omega}{8\pi^2}$$

Applying $\lambda\omega = 2\pi$ twice gives:

$$AM = \frac{m_{FR}}{2\omega}$$

The correct dimensionality can be obtained by reintroducing a factor of c^2 :

$$AM = \frac{m_{FR}c^2}{2\omega}$$

This is the AM for a single cell, but the mass of the entire structure is just the sum of all the masses of the cells, so the total AM for the structure is

$$AM_{stru} = \frac{m_{stru}c^2}{2\omega} \tag{5}$$

The correct scaling for RWQM to match QM is established later in Section 4.4 where we develop equation 21, namely:

$$\omega_0 = \frac{m_0c^2}{\hbar}$$

i.e ω is the Compton frequency. Using this value in equation 5 gives

$$AM = \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

In summary, given the postulate, we have established that our structures, when properly scaled, have spin AM of $\hbar/2$. There is nothing 'intrinsic' (perhaps inexplicable would be a better term) about spin in RWQM. It is a calculable quantity requiring no further interpretation.

4. Structures in Motion We now move on to consider the motion of entire RWQM structures through the medium.

4.1. Phase Harmony

The structures identified above are stationary within the medium and are highly interlinked - every FR relies on the summed contributions from every other FR, the resultant contribution being the vector sum of the discriminated contributions, whose relative phase is variable. If nothing else changed, motion of structures through the medium would destroy the phase relationships. For example, a wave emitted from one FR to the next

FR in the direction of motion will have to travel further to reach the receding target. Its phase on arrival will be quite different from that for the stationary structure. We therefore assume that structures in motion must change in such a way that the phase relationships **are** maintained, and raise this 'Phase Harmony' (PH) to a principle for RWQM⁴. We would now like to calculate its consequences.

4.2. Phase Harmony in 1-Dimension In the present analysis, we ignore the fact that the stable structures identified above involve Phase Alternation (PA) between consecutive FRs. In fact, we ignore FR phases completely: PH only requires that phase relationships remain *unchanged* by motion and says nothing about what those relationships might actually be. We initially restrict attention to a row of FRs along the x -axis, each having the same phase, and analyse motion in the $+x$ direction. The results obtained from this analysis turn out to be incorrect, but reveal features which are useful in understanding the relationship of RWQM to Schrödinger's equation and in subsequently developing the correct form.

For a structure at rest in the medium we envision that the FRs are spiral wave generators which are one wavelength apart and have identical phases. Waves in the $+x$ direction arrive at the next (and indeed, every subsequent) FR in phase with that FR. Likewise, waves in the $-x$ direction arrive in phase, but the phase differs by π radians, as is required to give Phase Direction Correlation. The resultant sum of the $+$ and $-$ waves is a standing wave with nodes at each FR which could be described by the real part of:

$$\vec{\Psi} = e^{i\left(\frac{\omega_0 x}{c} - \omega_0 t\right)} \quad (6)$$

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} = e^{i\left(-\frac{\omega_0 x}{c} - \omega_0 t + \pi\right)} \quad (7)$$

(We are completely ignoring amplitudes in this analysis, and must be careful not to give them any meaning in the results which follow.) Now we consider motion of the whole file of FRs at velocity v in the x direction: if phase harmony is to be maintained there must be a modified standing wave which still has the FRs at its nodes. The waves emitted along the $+x$ axis have their frequency raised by the Doppler effect, whilst those in the $-x$ direction have frequency lowered. The modified standing wave arises from the combined Doppler-shifted waves. Using the notation that $\vec{\omega}$ and $\overleftarrow{\omega}$ denote the shifted frequencies in the right and left directions we have:

⁴ Of course, this term was coined by de Broglie at the birth of quantum mechanics to associate the phase of a matter wave with the phase of a clock travelling with the 'particle', as observed by a stationary observer. RWQM has replaced the model of a discrete particle with a grid of FRs which in some sense respect the de Broglie postulate. However, the principle has been extended to apply to every interaction between FRs: the postulate is that motion through the medium must not change phase relationships between them.

$$\vec{\omega} = \frac{\omega_0}{1 - v/c}$$

$$\overleftarrow{\omega} = \frac{\omega_0}{1 + v/c}$$

Inserting these into 6 and 7, summing and removing the π by inserting a minus sign gives:

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} + \overrightarrow{\Psi} = e^{i\left(\frac{\vec{\omega}x}{c} - \vec{\omega}t\right)} - e^{i\left(-\frac{\overleftarrow{\omega}x}{c} - \overleftarrow{\omega}t\right)} \tag{8}$$

Equation 8 can be manipulated algebraically to the following form:

$$\overleftarrow{\Psi} + \overrightarrow{\Psi} = -2 \sin \left[\left(\frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) \frac{x}{c} - \left(\frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) t \right] \sin \left[\left(\frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) \frac{x}{c} - \left(\frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2} \right) t \right] \tag{9}$$

(The minus sign amounts to a phase shift of π which could be reabsorbed back into either of the product sinusoids). The combined 'phase harmony' wave has been expressed as the product of two travelling sinusoids, both moving towards the right. Inspection of the first sinusoid shows that it has angular frequency which is the average of the two Doppler shifted frequencies, but its wave vector is small, being the difference between these two quantities. For reasons which will become apparent, this sinusoid is denoted as p (phase). The second sinusoid has a relatively small frequency but wave vector which is the average of the two Doppler shifted frequencies. Again, for reasons discussed below, this is denoted as s (standing).

The various characteristics of the s and p sinusoids can be evaluated by substitution from the Doppler shift equations, using:

$$\omega_p = \frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2}; \quad k_p = \frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2c}; \quad \omega_s = \frac{\vec{\omega} - \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2}; \quad k_s = \frac{\vec{\omega} + \overleftarrow{\omega}}{2c}$$

For example, to find the propagation velocity of the standing sinusoid we put:

$$v_s = \frac{\omega_s}{k_s}$$

and after a simple but tedious calculation show that $v_s = v$, confirming that the standing sinusoid moves at the velocity of the structure.

Similar calculations show that the spacing of the spiral generators (indicated by the locations of the nodes of the standing waves) is reduced by the factor $1/\gamma^2$ (they must be closer together) and their rotation rate is reduced to

$$\omega_s = \frac{\gamma^2 \omega_0 v}{c} \tag{10}$$

The p wave gives the relative phase of the generators, and has wave vector

$$k_p = \frac{\gamma^2 \omega_0 v}{c^2} \tag{11}$$

At non-relativistic velocities (i.e. neglecting the γ^2 factor) it is proportional to the velocity of the structure. It is here that RWQM and the Schrödinger equation make contact, the latter being constructed on the basis of a wave vector with magnitude proportional to the velocity of the particle via the de Broglie relationship $p = \hbar k$. The results quoted above are non-relativistic. To obtain relativistic results we must re-analyse for 2 or 3 dimensions.

4.3. 2 and 3 Dimensions We have developed the concept of PH in one dimension because it best illustrates the ontology for the non-relativistic Schrödinger equation, i.e. the p and s sinusoids and the association of a phase gradient k_p with the velocity. For higher dimensions we require that phase harmony is also retained with FRs to some degree orthogonal with the direction of motion. To achieve this we first develop equation 39 in **C** giving the following general expression for calculating the phase separation between any two FRs within a structure in motion through the ether:

$$\Phi_{ST'} = \phi_{ST} - \frac{\omega\gamma^2}{c^2} \left[l_x v + \sqrt{c^2 (l_x^2 + l_y^2 + l_z^2) - v^2 (l_y^2 + l_z^2)} \right] \quad (12)$$

In this equation the x axis is labelled as the direction of motion, and

- S is the location of the source FR at time $t = 0$
- T is the location of the target at $t = 0$
- T' is the target location when the phase emanating from the source at $t = 0$ arrives.
- ϕ is the angle between the phase directions of the two FRs at $t = 0$
- ω is the rotation rate of the moving FRs
- l_x is the distance between them parallel to the direction of motion.
- l_y, l_z are the distances between S and T perpendicular to the direction of motion
- Φ is the relative phase between the arriving wave and the phase of the target FR at arrival. It is this which must be unchanged by motion to ensure Phase Harmony.

We can now demonstrate that RWQM with Phase Harmony is Lorentz invariant by substituting the appropriate expressions in equation 12. For time dilation and length contraction we have

$$\omega = \omega(v) = \frac{\omega_0}{\gamma}, \quad l_x = l_x(v) = \frac{l_x}{\gamma} \quad (13)$$

We also need ϕ_{ST} , and we note that this is given by the x separation multiplied by the phase gradient in the x direction:

$$\phi_{ST} = l_x(v)k_p(v) \quad (14)$$

We can use equation 11 to find what the wave vector would be with frequency becoming velocity dependent as describe in equations 13

$$k_p = \frac{\gamma^2 \omega_0 v}{c^2} \Rightarrow k_p(v) = \frac{\gamma^2 \omega_0(v) v}{c^2} = \frac{\gamma \omega_0 v}{c^2} \quad (15)$$

Substituting for the contracted length and the dilated time in equations 14 the γ factors cancel giving:

$$\phi_{ST} = \frac{l_x \omega_0 v}{c^2} \quad (16)$$

Substituting this and the relationships in (13) into equation (12) gives

$$\Phi_{ST'} = \frac{l_x \omega_0 v}{c^2} - \frac{\omega_0 \gamma^2}{\gamma c^2} \left[\frac{l_x v}{\gamma} + \sqrt{c^2 \left(\frac{l_x^2}{\gamma^2} + l_y^2 + l_z^2 \right) - v^2 (l_y^2 + l_z^2)} \right] \quad (17)$$

Opening the square brackets results in the first two terms cancelling leaving:

$$\Phi_{ST'} = -\frac{\omega_0 \gamma}{c^2} \sqrt{c^2 \left(\frac{l_x^2}{\gamma^2} + l_y^2 + l_z^2 \right) - v^2 (l_y^2 + l_z^2)} \quad (18)$$

Finally, manipulating the terms in the square root leads to:

$$\Phi_{ST'} = -\frac{\omega_0 \gamma}{c^2} \frac{c}{\gamma} \sqrt{l_x^2 + l_y^2 + l_z^2} \quad (19)$$

The γ s cancel showing that the phase difference is invariant under motion through the medium when the Lorentz transform is applied. Essentially, structures must undergo the Lorentz length contraction and time dilation. For reference, the relativistic wave characteristics for the structures are provided in D

In summary, the Phase Harmony constraint requires that for FRs moving at a velocity v through the ether:

- the spacing between FRs in the direction of motion be reduced by the relationship $\lambda_v = \lambda_0/\gamma$ (SR length contraction)
- the frequency of rotation of FRs be reduced by the relationship $\omega_v = \omega_0/\gamma$ (SR time dilation)
- a spatial phase variation be applied to the FRs in accordance with the phase gradient $\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\omega_0 \gamma v}{c^2}$ (the velocity element of de Broglie's $p = \hbar k$)

The application of these requirements is illustrated in OLR5 and OLR6 . OLR5 shows a 1 dimensional row of FRs (but applying the proper 2/3D SR constraints) moving to the right at various velocities. The blue and red lines represent wave fronts travelling at $\pm c$ positioned so that they are in phase with the FRs as they pass them. Phase harmony is apparent as the waves pass every FR in phase. The shorter spacing and the slower rotation is obvious when $v/c = 0.8$. OLR6 shows a 2 dimensional field of FRs moving a $v/c = 0.4$. The blue and red lines are as in OLR5, while the green and yellow lines are introduced to show that transverse waves are also in phase harmony.

4.3.1. The Ether Assumption

In Section 1.2 we stated our assumption of a massive ether, but noted that we must be able to demonstrate the compatibility of such an assumption with the experimentally established facts of Special Relativity. In this section we have done this - up to a point. What we have shown is that Phase harmony can only be achieved if structures have slower rotation rates and length contraction in the manner described by Lorentz, but this is not the whole story. In addition, there will be amplitude effects. At relativistic velocities forward waves travel much longer distances between FRs while backward waves travel shorter distances. The ramifications of this are not clear, but any effects so caused would be very small at low velocities and Special Relativity is the correct low speed asymptotic behaviour predicted by RWQM. 'Low' speeds encompass most practical applications, such as measuring the speed of light in an earth based system and velocity related time dilation in GPS satellites. The nature of any deviations from SR at relativistic velocities is an open question.

It is worth noting that for RWQM, SR behaviour such as we have described is an emergent property. We have not applied the Relativity Postulate (RP) to the theory. The need for SR behaviour has emerged from the deeper principle of Phase Harmony. It would be wrong to say that RWQM implies the RP because we have not considered amplitude effects. Perhaps we are putting limits on the validity of the RP? Clearly more work is required in this area.

As we have already pointed out in Section 3.1, the 'mass' of the ether does not contribute directly to the mass and angular momentum aspects of the structure - rather, it is the energy carried by the ether waves which, to the extent to which it is spatially localized, constitutes the structure (particle) mass and contributes to the angular momentum.

4.4. Scaling RWQM Thus far we have not attempted to place a scale on the RWQM model.

The analysis has been essentially geometric and has applied to a mathematical model for moving spiral wave structures with phase harmony. We have considered unit grids and waves having wavelength equal to the grid size so that $\omega_0 = 2\pi$, (perhaps modified in the presence of potential fields as discussed in Section 2.3.1). We have not clarified what the wavelength must be to replicate QM and will now do this by considering the de Broglie-Einstein equations:

$$p = \hbar k; \quad E = \hbar\omega = mc^2 \quad (20)$$

These were instrumental in the derivation of the Schrödinger equation. We have not thus far considered how mass would fit in to the model, but we have a plausible candidate in the frequency of the p wave

$$\tilde{\omega}_p = \gamma\omega_0$$

as it displays the correct behaviour relativistically. Put:

$$\beta\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$$

where β is a constant of proportionality, and adopt the convention that the tilde refers to the motion dependent mass. Using equation 15 i.e:

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\gamma\omega_0 v}{c^2}; \quad \tilde{\omega}_p = \gamma\omega_0$$

we can show that

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_p v}{c^2}$$

so right hand side of the de Broglie equation can be constructed as:

$$\hbar\tilde{k}_p \Rightarrow \hbar\frac{\tilde{\omega}_p v}{c^2}$$

The left hand side is

$$p = v\tilde{m} = v\beta\tilde{\omega}_p$$

Equating LHS and RHS and cancelling terms gives:

$$\beta = \frac{\hbar}{c^2}$$

Reinserting this into the mass postulate $\beta\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$ gives:

$$\frac{\hbar}{c^2}\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}$$

or:

$$\hbar\tilde{\omega}_p = \tilde{m}c^2$$

which are the two Einstein expressions for energy. They hold for all v and in particular for $v = 0$ which is the rest mass equation, when $\tilde{\omega}_p = \omega_0$ and $\tilde{m} = m_0$. Re-arranging gives:

$$\omega_0 = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\hbar} \tag{21}$$

This is the Compton frequency for the electron. The p wave becomes

$$\sin \left[\frac{\gamma m_0 v}{\hbar} x - \frac{m_0 \gamma c^2}{\hbar} t \right] \tag{22}$$

The conclusion is that we can scale the geometric RWQM theory to the de Broglie-Einstein equations provided that $\tilde{\omega}_p$ is indicative of mass and that the rest frequency of rotation of the FRs is the Compton frequency. It is well known that the potential required to confine an electron within a Compton wavelength is sufficient to create a second particle. Thus, the Compton wavelength is the distance at which single particle QM solutions become meaningless. Likewise, RWQM structures, which involve interactions between FRs separated by this distance, cannot exist at this scale. It is also the scale at which Zitterbewegung solutions of the Dirac equation arise. The RWQM scale is already of great significance in QM.

4.5. Comparison of RWQM and Dirac Solutions for a Free Particle

Solution of the Dirac equation for a free particle moving through a rest frame leads to four linked equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (E - m_0c^2) U_1 & 0U_2 & -cp_xU_3 & -c(p_y - ip_z) U_4 \\ 0U_1 & (E - m_0c^2) U_2 & -c(p_y + ip_z) U_3 & cp_xU_4 \\ -cp_xU_1 & -c(p_y - ip_z) U_2 & (E + m_0c^2) U_3 & 0U_4 \\ -c(p_y + ip_z) U_1 & +cp_xU_2 & 0U_3 & (E + m_0c^2) U_4 \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

where we have some freedom to choose the U 's. For example, putting $U_1 = 1$ and $U_2 = 0$ allows U_3 and U_4 to be determined

$$U_3 = \frac{cp_x}{E + m_0c^2}$$

$$U_4 = \frac{c(p_y + ip_z)}{E + m_0c^2}$$

Substituting these into the first equation gives:

$$E - m_0c^2 - \frac{c^2p_x^2}{E + m_0c^2} - \frac{c^2(p_y - ip_z)^2}{E + m_0c^2} = 0$$

Now if we restrict ourselves to motion in the $+x$ direction (which is aligned with the grid as we supposed in deriving the RWQM solution) we can eliminate the p_y and p_z terms, whence:

$$E^2 = c^2p_x^2 + (m_0c^2)^2$$

$$E = \pm\sqrt{c^2p_x^2 + (m_0c^2)^2}$$

We can remove a factor of $m_0^2c^4$ from the root to give:

$$E = \pm m_0c^2\sqrt{\frac{p_x^2}{m_0^2c^2} + 1}$$

Here, m_0 is the rest energy but p_x is the relativistic momentum, which depends on the relativistic mass given by $p_x = m_vv$ where $m_v = \gamma m_0$ We can now substitute for p_x^2 and after some algebraic manipulation arrive at:

$$E = \pm m_0c^2\gamma \tag{23}$$

Now consider our p sinusoid, being the first factor of equation 22, i.e.:

$$e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(\gamma m_0vx - m_0c^2\gamma t)} \tag{24}$$

Applying the energy operator $\hat{E} = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ gives:

$$E = i\hbar \frac{-im_0c^2\gamma}{\hbar}$$

$$E = m_0c^2\gamma \quad (25)$$

which is the same as the positive root of equation 23. For a free particle (structure) RWQM predicts the same energies as the relativistic Dirac equation.

4.6. Spin Representation Our consideration of Phase Harmony requirements has led us to an understanding of the spacing, angular frequency and phase gradient consequences of motion through the ether. However, a complication arises if we want to incorporate spin into the model because we must then consider the direction of rotation as well as the frequency. We must allow positive and negative values for ω to describe this. However, it is an absolute requirement that the p and s waves both move in the same direction. If we flip the sign of ω then we must also flip the sign of k to ensure this.

But this means that for anticlockwise spin we should be applying $p = -\hbar k$ for the de Broglie relationship. The situation is even more bizarre, since if we look at the structure from the opposite side, the spin direction flips again and we are back to $p = \hbar k$! It seems that this problem does arise in interpreting the Dirac equation. On occasion it is necessary to change the sign of the momentum and to invent bizarre physical justifications for doing so, such as matter travelling backwards in time.

4.7. Conclusions Regarding Motion of Structures The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The principle of Phase Harmony within structures in motion through the medium is consistent with the Lorentz transform. We have required neither the Relativity Principle (RP) nor the postulate of a constant speed of light in all reference frames to show this.
- The RWQM assumption of a medium (ether) does not disqualify it, because the Lorentz transform masks its existence.
- RWQM with Phase Harmony gives the same energy for a free particle as the Dirac equation.

5. Pauli Exclusion Principle The Pauli Exclusion Principle is a central tenet of QM. Here

we would like to show that it is a direct consequence of the Phase Alternation exhibited by RWQM solutions. Phase Alternation in a 3-D grid is illustrated in Figure 14. Red and

Figure 14. Grid With Phase Alternation

blue dots indicate phase differing by π radians. Now consider contributions received at point A at the centre of the cube. Contributions from a and e have the same direction at A relative to the plane of rotation. As they have opposite phase their contribution will cancel out. Likewise for c and g , h and d and b and f . Points like A at the centre of any cube feel no contribution. Likewise, FRs in a grid of all points like A would not interact with points a, b, \dots . This contrasts with the findings for a simple planar array illustrated in OLR 1, where the presence of FRs of one spin leads automatically to FRs having opposite spin. In 3-dimensions we can have single occupation of a quantum state. A second electron of opposite spin can co-exist at the interspersed cubic points like A , but the presence of one does not require the presence of the other. This is the ontology of the Pauli Exclusion Principle.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

Comparison of Interpretations

RWQM	Facet	QM/QFT
$\hbar/2$ derivable using COM calculation for PDC. Not a consequence of relativity.	Spin Angular Momentum	'Intrinsic $\hbar/2$ ' Predicted by Dirac equation from relativistic considerations.
Calculable from Phase Gradient within structure which has direct interpretation.	Orbital Angular Momentum	Calculable from phase gradient which has no direct interpretation.
Demonstrable consequence of Phase Alternation in structures.	Pauli Exclusion	Initially a 'principle'. A consequence of spin-statistics theorem.
Complex conjugated, reversed spin, potential inverted RWQM solutions are in phase harmony	Antimatter	Negative energy electrons? Electrons going backwards in time? Positrons going forward in time.
Scale matches the s wavelength. Structures become impossible as this size is approached.	Compton Scale Effects i.e Zitter and Darwin term	'Motion at $\pm c$ over \approx Compton wavelength? 'Smearing' of electric charge. Maximal containment particle distance.
Modification of rest mass frequency which is required to give real eigenvalues.	Origin of 'Energy Levels'	Schrödinger \Rightarrow 'frequency' of wave function. Dirac \Rightarrow modification of the rest mass and hence frequency.
Reverse direction of p wave of no consequence.	Depiction of spin orientation.	Some Dirac 'Particles' interpreted as having negative momenta.
'Phase Harmony' \Rightarrow Lorentz invariance as asymptotic behaviour at low velocities.	Relativistic?	Schrödinger equation non-relativistic. Dirac equation relativistic .
Energy operator applied to RWQM free particle wavefunction gives same energy as Dirac plane wave solution.	Energy of free particle	'Plane wave solution of Dirac equation has same energy as RWQM.

As noted in the introduction, our direction of travel differs from the normal approach to the interpretation of QM/QFT. Our model starts from its own postulates, derives consequences, and maps them onto facets of QM/QFT. (The extent to which this has proved possible has amazed the author!) The comparison is summarized in the Table.

Despite attempts to dress the foundations of QM/QFT with direct physical significance, they are at heart mathematical constructions. For example, the simple introduction to the Schrödinger equation in most textbooks will describe the Hamiltonian as the sum of kinetic and potential terms, originally conceptualized as applied to a massive charged point particle moving in an electric field. These interpretations become increasingly tenuous the deeper we go, but the mathematics has got something right and the equation is extremely useful in an 'engineering' sense - we can use it in a myriad of applications. Interpreted in RWQM terms Schrödinger's equation 'works' because at non-relativistic velocities structures are partially described by a phase wave whose wave vector is proportional to the velocity of the structure (or its negative); while Phase Alternation requires that the shape of eigenstructures be controlled by the second spatial derivative of the field. But at a superficial level physics does not need to know this: once the equation exists we can continue by pure mathematics to develop the entire science of non-relativistic QM. It is hardly surprising that subsequent interpretations are hard to understand. The probability interpretation is a case in point. We must somehow recognise that an electron has a presence which is distributed in space, even while insisting that it is a point particle. There is no such difficulty in RWQM: the electron *is* extended in space. Similarly, in QFT, we can recognise that particles correspond to some 'excitation' of a field whose main properties are understood, but we have no picture of what such an excitation 'is': QFT only partially meets Bohm's[1] prediction mentioned in the Introduction.

6.1. Relationship to Other Theories

6.1.1. de Broglie-Bohm

The de Broglie-Bohm (dBB) Pilot Wave theory [12] [13] postulates a real massive point particle whose location is guided by a 'Pilot' Schrödinger wave function. Perhaps the easiest way to compare RWQM and dBB is by examining the different interpretations of the Twin Slit experiment. In the dBB interpretation the entity approaching the slits consists of a Schrödinger pilot wave function with the point particle embedded in it. The probabilistic nature of QM resides in the initial location of the particle within the wave: the probability of it *being* at a particular location is controlled via the normal QM $\psi^*\psi$ formulation. Subsequently the wave passes through both slits and the particle through one or the other as controlled by the 'guidance' equation. The two branches of the wave function proceed to interfere with each other, which in turn controls the guidance of the

particle until it finally interacts with the point on the detector screen at which it arrives and the wave function collapses. Thus, the destination point is controlled deterministically by the initial position of the particle within the wave, together with the evolution of the wave function which proceeds as if the particle was not present. But what was the wave function? Was it something physical, in which case how did it collapse, or was it even more mysteriously just a mathematical artefact?

We can speculatively interpret the same experiment as seen by RWQM. The arriving structure is a distributed electron whose mass resides in the FRs pro-rata to $\psi^*\psi$ for the Schrödinger wave which envelopes it. The structure passes through both slits and the wave lobes interfere beyond them, exactly as for the dBB case, leading to the expected interference pattern for $\psi^*\psi$ across the whole surface of the detector. It is at this point that the probabilistic aspect enters for RWQM. We assume that there are myriads of potential detection points across the plate but that the probability of an interaction for any of them is very low, and is proportional to the local value of $\psi^*\psi$. 'Detection' is the result of an entirely physical collapse of the distributed electron structure into the absorbing point. We could even envisage multiple sites competing for the electron. Detection is only complete when one of them 'wins'. Other theories, such as Stochastic Electrodynamics (see below) could provide insights into the nature of this collapse.

The two interpretations are completely different. Nevertheless, they share one important mathematical feature: the importance of the guidance equation. This comes to the fore in calculating orbital angular momentum. dBB envisages that electrons in orbitals rotate around the nucleus at velocities controlled by the phase gradient of the guiding Schrödinger wave. Constant angular momentum arises because velocities so calculated are inversely proportional to the radius. A weakness of this interpretation is that velocities at very small radii must be relativistic. As discussed in Section 3.1, RWQM applies the guidance equation to calculate the correct AM, but interprets momentum as arising from the energy flux within the structure. The only things 'moving' are physical acoustic waves so there are no relativistic difficulties in this interpretation.

6.1.2. Stochastic Electrodynamics

Stochastic Electrodynamics (SED) [15] is based on a charged point particle undergoing rapid oscillatory motion arising from interaction with a stochastic electromagnetic zero point vacuum field. In comparison, the RWQM distributed electron structure arises from interaction with a postulated stochastic acoustic vacuum field which is not assumed to be quantized. Despite these very different assumptions there are strong points of contact between the two theories. SED concludes that the electron takes on an effective structure having size and frequency related to the Compton wavelength and Compton frequency respectively. This is exactly the description we would apply to a single FR in RWQM!

Further, the link between SED and the de Broglie wave [16] is cast in exactly the same terms as our arguments in sections 4.2 and 4.3; namely the forward and backward Doppler shifted waves from the extended SED electron structure in motion. The key difference is that SED is viewing a single effectively structured particle, while RWQM involves interaction between many FRs with Compton characteristics within a moving structure. RWQM is thus able to explain the emergence of SR in terms of Lorentz distance contraction between FRs, while this is not available to the SED single structured electron.

6.2. Final Thoughts The author cannot resist one further flight of fancy. If RWQM is the ontology of QM/QFT it might suggest a fresh explanation of 'Dark Matter'. Given the stochastic nature of the acoustic vacuum field, it is certain that small clumps of interacting FRs (FRagments!) must form and disperse continuously throughout the vacuum. What if these were gravitationally active during their short lifetime?

There is much to do in the development of RWQM and as it is the work of a single author working in isolation the findings so far must of course be checked independently. The Author may not be in a position to pursue the study much further and hopes that this paper will stimulate further work on the subject by others.

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A. Acoustic Spin By choosing to represent the acoustic field as the four-divergence of a

bivector potential $a \sim (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ Burns et al [4] show that (with the gauge assumption $\mathbf{b} = 0$) the spin density S is given by

$$S = \frac{\sqrt{\rho}}{c} \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{a} \tag{26}$$

where ρ is the density of the medium, c is the speed of wave propagation in the medium and \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{v} can be associated with displacement and velocity fields respectively. We can apply this to the four wave prototype by setting:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} = & a_0 \hat{\mathbf{i}} [\cos(kx - \omega t) + \cos(-kx - \omega t + \pi)] \\ & + a_0 \hat{\mathbf{j}} [\cos(ky - \omega t + \pi/2) + \cos(-ky - \omega t + 3\pi/2)] \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Following Burns et al the velocity field can be found as

$$\mathbf{v} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial t} + \nabla \times \mathbf{b}; \quad \mathbf{b} = 0 \tag{28}$$

Figure 15. Spin density for 4 waves in Phase Direction Correlation calculated following Burns et al [4]

and performing the cross product in equation 26, gives the spin density:

$$S = \hat{\mathbf{k}} \frac{4a_0^2\omega}{c^2} \sin(xk) \sin(yk) \tag{29}$$

Setting $a_0 = 1$, $c = 1$ and $\lambda = 1$ i.e $\omega = k = 2\pi$, this function is plotted in Figure 15, over the same range as the animation. While spin density (which arises from locally elliptical motion of particles forming the medium) follows the familiar checkerboard pattern, it is rather more difficult to interpret the complete motion without first seeing the animation. For the parameters chosen the total spin integrated over a single spin cell of $1/2 \times 1/2$ is $8/\pi$. Over a square of four such cells (and therefore over the complete field), the spin integrates to zero. The key findings for orthogonal waves such as these is that:

- the spin density does not depend on the density of the medium
- the spin density varies as the square of the amplitude
- the spin density is proportional to the frequency.

B. Calculating Contributions The objective is to calculate the extent to which waves

passing through a point contribute to Phase Direction Correlation. Start by considering a 'phase arrow' as depicted in Figure 16 which is the mathematical expression for a wave travelling in the $+x$ direction, as will be the case when the signs of the x and t terms are opposite. Here, k is positive, so will be increasing with x as shown in the first phase arrow. The second arrow describes a short time δ later. The phase at the red line was π in the first arrow, but becomes less than π , showing that phase at a point reduces with time.

Figure 16. A Phase Arrow

$$\phi = kx - \omega t$$

Figure 17. The top pair of figures show phase arrows from cardinal points in PDC with clockwise or anticlockwise ordering. The second row tabulates the results of either summing or taking the difference between phase and direction. For clockwise ordering the sum is required while for anticlockwise ordering it is the difference.

(a) Clockwise

(b) Anticlockwise

Direction	Phase	Sum	Difference
$3\pi/2$	0	$3\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$
π	$\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$	$\pi/2$
$\pi/2$	π	$3\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$
0	$3\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$	$\pi/2$

Direction	Phase	Sum	Difference
$3\pi/2$	0	$3\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$
0	$\pi/2$	$\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$
$\pi/2$	π	$3\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$
π	$3\pi/2$	$\pi/2$	$3\pi/2$

We can use phase arrows to depict the situation of four plane waves in PDC from the cardinal directions. In Figure 17a the direction of the PDC is clockwise. The arrow from the north is set to be arriving with phase 0. The arrow from the east must have phase 0 in a quarter of a revolution's time, so its current phase must be $\pi/2$ and so on. The opposite ordering applies in Figure 17b. We require that each arrow contribute the same amount to PDC. The Tables show that this can be done by taking the sum of the phase and direction for clockwise spin, and the difference between them for anticlockwise spin, and we call this the discriminated contribution.

Now we consider calculation of the arriving phases (rather than how we treat them once they arrive). In Figure 18 we consider the wavefront for an anticlockwise spiral wave shown in red. For a source at S and a target at A the phase arriving is clearly 2π . If the target is moved to T at the same distance as A, then the phase is increased by the amount θ_{ST} . For a clockwise spin, Figure 19 the result is the opposite - the phase is reduced by θ_{ST} .

Now we can combine the results for

- finding the phases of the arriving waves and
- treating them to calculate their PDC contribution

For the anticlockwise state, we note that the phase offset between source and target is given by

$$\phi_{ST} = d/\lambda \tag{30}$$

(not to be confused with θ_{ST} !) The phase arriving at the target is

$$\phi_T = \phi_S + \phi_{ST} + \theta_{ST} \tag{31}$$

i.e the phase of the source plus the phase arising from the distance between source and target plus the correction for the direction from source to target as explained in Figure 18.

The anticlockwise spin discriminated contribution is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Direction} - \text{Phase} &= \theta_{ST} - \phi_T \\ &= \theta_{ST} - (\phi_S + \phi_{ST} + \theta_{ST}) \\ &= -\phi_S - \phi_{ST} \\ &= -\phi_S - d/\lambda \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

The discriminated contribution does not depend on the direction. Applying a similar process in the clockwise case we get

$$\phi_T = \phi_S + \phi_{ST} - \theta_{ST} \tag{33}$$

i.e the phase of the source plus the phase arising from the distance between source and target **minus** the correction for the direction from source to target as explained in Figure

Figure 19. Applying similar reasoning to the clockwise case shows that the arriving phase is less than 2π by the angle θ_{ST}

Figure 20. Phase shift due to motion

be some difference between the phase of T and S , say

$$\phi_{ST} = P_T(0) - P_S(0) \tag{35}$$

Now let the whole structure move in the $+x$ direction at velocity v . After a period of time Δt the target will have moved to T' having coordinates $(l_x + v\Delta t, l_y, l_z)$. Applying Pythagoras we can deduce that

$$(ct)^2 = (l_x + v\Delta t)^2 + l_y^2 + l_z^2 \tag{36}$$

This is quadratic in Δt with solution, using the substitution $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$:

$$\Delta t = \frac{l_x v \gamma^2}{c^2} \pm \frac{\gamma^2}{c^2} \sqrt{c^2 (l_x^2 + l_y^2 + l_z^2) - v^2 (l_y^2 + l_z^2)} \tag{37}$$

Knowing this time the phase difference between T' and T can be calculated. It is $-\omega\Delta t$ (minus because T is at an earlier time than T'), where ω is the angular frequency of the FRs. We require the phase of the wave from the source arriving at the target at time Δt and this is simply $P_S(0)$. (Think of it as a "phase bullet" fired from the source at $t = 0$ at velocity c . In time Δt it has covered the distance $c\Delta t$ and that is the distance from S to T'). In this same time the target phase has changed by the amount $-\omega\Delta t$ meaning it now has phase $P_T(0) - \omega\Delta t$. Hence the difference between the target phase and the phase of the wave arriving from the source, say $\Phi_{ST'}$ is

$$\Phi_{ST'} = P_T(0) - \omega\Delta t - P_S(0) \tag{38}$$

But $P_T(0) - P_S(0)$ has been defined in 35 as ϕ_{ST} . Hence the required general relationship is

$$\Phi_{ST'} = \phi_{ST} - \frac{\omega\gamma^2}{c^2} \left[l_x v + \sqrt{c^2 (l_x^2 + l_y^2 + l_z^2) - v^2 (l_y^2 + l_z^2)} \right] \tag{39}$$

D. Wave Characteristics for Relativistic Structures

Box 1 Relativistic Expressions for p and s Sinusoids

ω_0 and λ_0 are the angular frequency and spatial separation of the FRs at rest. ω_v and λ_v are the moving values

$$\omega_v = \omega_0/\gamma; \quad \lambda_v = \lambda_0/\gamma$$

$$\tilde{k}_s = \frac{\omega_0\gamma}{c}$$

$$\tilde{\omega}_s = \frac{\omega_0 v \gamma}{c}$$

$$\tilde{\lambda}_s = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_0\gamma} \Rightarrow \tilde{\lambda}_s = \lambda_0/\gamma \Rightarrow \tilde{\lambda}_s = \lambda_v$$

$$\tilde{v}_s = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_s}{\tilde{k}_s} = v$$

$$\tilde{k}_p = \frac{\omega_0\gamma v}{c^2} = \frac{k_0\gamma v}{c}$$

$$\tilde{\omega}_p = \omega_0\gamma$$

$$\tilde{\lambda}_p = \frac{2\pi c^2}{\omega_0\gamma v}$$

$$\tilde{v}_p = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_p}{\tilde{k}_p} = \frac{c^2}{v}$$

$$\tilde{v}_s \tilde{v}_p = c^2$$

Group velocities:

$$\tilde{v}_{p,g} = \tilde{v}_p$$

$$\tilde{v}_{s,g} = v$$